

Advance science by publishing without profit

Birgit C. Schlick-Steiner¹, Brent C. Emerson² & Florian M. Steiner^{1*}

¹ Department of Ecology, University of Innsbruck, 6020 Innsbruck, Austria

² Instituto de Productos Naturales y Agrobiología (IPNA-CSIC), 38206 San Cristóbal de La Laguna, Canary Islands, Spain

* Corresponding author. Email: florian.m.steiner@uibk.ac.at

Scientific publishing is an evolving process, which has seen substantial change over recent decades that can be traced back to the commercialization of scientific publication itself. Science is a growing business, where growth is fueled by the research that scientists produce. However, this is not a healthy business model. At least not for science. Here, we take stock of the business of scientific publication, structured as a series of reflective questions. In doing so, we look at how we got to where we are, what problems it presents, and what future options are available for improvement.

Should everyone be able to make all their research output available to everyone? The traditional answer to this question has been *no* – and science has incorporated pre-publication filters as regulatory mechanisms (Figure 1). In the early days, scientific publication was facilitated by authors being recognized or established within the scientific community, often requiring membership of a scientific society (1). Peer reviewing has emerged as a universal contemporary pre-publication filter. Thus, there has been a shift away from perceived reputation (e.g., society membership) toward perceived merit (peer review), which, in theory, should democratize scientific publishing, and in doing so advance science through broader participation.

Who pays to make research output accessible? In the early days, the reader paid, often via membership of a scientific society, that then made their publications available to their members. Subsequently, research institutions assumed a more prominent role, through institutional subscriptions that paid for their researchers to be able to read. As publishing began to scale up, publishing houses became increasingly aware of profit potential. What followed was an intense commercialization of scientific publishing, with roots that can be traced back to Robert Maxwell, who is credited with the establishment of the high-profit, paywall-driven model (2, 3, 4, 5). Finally, since the beginning of this century, a paywall-derived open-access (OA) initiative has led to a gradual paradigm shift from subscription-based model to one of individual article processing charges (APC). Within this APC model, the author pays so the reader can read. APCs are paid centrally by an institution or research-funding agency, or directly from research grants, or even personally.

Is OA publishing living up to its promise? OA publishing, as an idealized concept, is a win-win situation. Scientific publication is first filtered by scientific peers for quality, robustness and relevance (pre-publication filtering), with OA publishing then removing the institution-based filter for access to scientific publication. Everyone can read everything. However, what promised to remove inequalities by making science available to everyone, has backfired, and badly. Underpinning this failure is the APCs, which have increased

strongly (to, e.g., 3000-5000 EUR per article) to very strongly (exceeding 10,000 EUR per article), with effective waiver programs in place just rarely. The scale of APCs seems hard to justify from the perspective of individual scientists. Why do I have to pay so much to make my research available? The answer is that your research is the bedrock of a business model with profit margins of up to 40% for commercial publishers (6, 7, 8). However, one is not a beneficiary of this business model. In fact, it is worse than that, one is a “consumable”.

Can we explain the current system of who pays for publishing to a non-scientist, without appearing to have been conned? No, we can't. As far back as 2005, it was already noted that “the industry structure can only be described as bizarre – the state funds most research, pays the salaries of most of those checking the quality of the research (in peer-review processes) and then buys most of the published product” (6). And the publishing costs have only gotten worse since then. While once holding the promise of science for all through OA, APCs have now become a strong pre-publication filter (Figure 1).

What determines the cost of APCs? Three factors are relevant. First, scientists typically evaluate each other and their output using quantitative measures, most notably the Impact Factor (IF) and derived metrics. These metrics are contentiously used as a measure of research quality, but are broadly recognized as problematic in this context (9). Second, and related to the first point, authors decide upon journals for the submission of their work to help advance their career or improve their prestige. If APCs are met by the author's institution or funding agency, money is less likely to be the primary factor for journal selection. Thus, competition between journals and publishers can be expected to act at the level of IF-based journal rankings and similar metrics, and not at that of the APCs. Third, and derived from the first two points, as journal prestige (i.e., ranking based on IF) increases, so does demand to publish there, enabling APCs to be raised by the publisher. APCs from three journals from Nature Publishing Group provide an example: Communications Biology with IF = 5.1 and APC = 3650 EUR, Nature Communications with IF = 15.7 and APC = 6150 EUR, and Nature with IF = 48.5 and APC = 10,690 EUR. These three factors drive a vicious circle, increasing publication costs and in so doing deepening inequalities globally (see next section). Through publishers' platforms (and enhanced by individual decisions to, e.g., have login data saved), all kinds of granular user interaction data are collected, from search terms used, time spent at sites, to publications downloaded. These data enable publishers to better target their products, make tailored suggestions to researchers which papers to read (and cite), and even which journals to submit to. It is thus not surprising that data tracking has become a major pillar of the large publishers, building what has been termed a knowledge industry (2, 10).

How worried should we be about for-profit publishing? Very. It excludes researchers, and erodes the bang we get for each scientific buck in a number of ways. First, current profit-based OA publishing increases the gap between researchers in developed economies and all other countries. Nearly half of all researchers worldwide are potentially excluded from OA publishing because of financial constraints (Figure 2; exceptions exist where OA publishing is possible without APCs being charged, often termed “Diamond OA”, but these journals tend to have low visibility, 11). Disadvantaged researchers are concentrated in Africa, Asia, and South America (Figure 2). Second, by excluding possibly half of the world's researchers, APCs are also hindering scientific advance more generally, through unnecessary research duplication (7) when the work of APC-excluded researchers does not get attention. Third,

even if APCs can be met in a country, the money spent has effectively been diverted from scientific advance. APC money is largely from tax payers that flows directly into the purse of for-profit publishers. Considering that the annual budget for research and development globally exceeds 2 trillion USD (12), about half of it being public money (7), even a small percentage used for APCs is an enormous amount of money. Finally, even in countries in which established researchers can afford high APCs, early-career and yet-to-be-established researchers that engage in grant-free research are more likely to be excluded (13).

Can we achieve the goal of OA science, and commit more of our science budgets to science? Yes. APCs are now a strong pre-publication filter that needs to be addressed, but it will require a bottom-up approach. We are already seeing signs of dissatisfaction and how action can be taken. Editorial teams can step down from for-profit journals and start new journals with not-for-profit publishers (e.g., 14). Funding agencies and research institutions could stop handing over money to researchers to pay APCs (as some funding agencies have already started to do; 15, 16). But that may simply expand the global catchment of the filter. One could appeal to publishers to implement this, but why would they? Indeed, it has been tried and failed (e.g. 14, 17). The core of the problem is how scientists themselves measure and value scientists. If scientists continue to look at IF and other derived metrics as a measure of individual worth, there would seem little motivation for a publisher to reduce APCs. The publication-for-profit dilemma, and the measurement of individual scientific worth, are two sides of the same coin, and need to be jointly considered to escape from the dilemma itself. One radical but viable approach brings us back to the first question – *should everyone be able to make their research available to everyone?*

From preprints to permaprints as an emerging pathway to OA without APCs

Preprint servers are already part of the scientific landscape, where preprints are acceptable citations (18), and are being proposed as relevant output for research assessment (19). How radical would it then be for a journal to host its own preprints? The idea would almost certainly meet with resistance from publishing houses, but among the pros and cons (Box 1) there are tangible ways for preprints to also provide some relief within a struggling peer review system. As a basis for discussion, we here sketch a framework (and acknowledge that details may need be refined based on dynamics after first implementation). Thus, standardized screening will be needed, to ensure that basic quality standards are met for initial preprint acceptance, possibly using AI as aid, but not as a decision-making tool. Once published, preprints can be live and evolvable versioned entities, where peers can comment and authors can respond. After a preset time period (such as half a year, but this could differ across fields), the preprints would then automatically turn into the endpoint for the readership, prohibiting any further change; to signal this status, they could be termed permaprints, for example. Visibility and prestige of papers would be constituted by comments made on and citations gathered by permaprints, that is, the reception by the scientific community of a specific paper could substitute metrics like the IF. Such a shift from pre- to post-publication filter may then also provide a way forward to address current issues with the review process. These include individual reviewer bias or conflict of interest that may influence editorial decisions, scientific trajectory driven by novelty-based reward, and publishing as a slow process (20) that has become open to fraud (21). And equally, if not more importantly, the, hitherto APC-excluded half of all scientists could fully engage within the global scientific community – and science could advance to its full potential.

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Figure 1: Pre-publication filters and exemplary negative consequences within the open-access oriented publishing system in science.

Figure 2: Numbers of researchers per continent for whom publishing in journals that require payment of Article Processing Charges likely is accessible (likely included; M = million) vs. likely is not accessible (likely excluded); percentages of researchers likely excluded are added for each continent. Researchers “likely included” are based in countries classified as developed economies (22) and researchers “likely excluded” in any of the other countries. Estimated numbers of researchers based on Our World in Data (23, 24); no data available for 59 of the 203 countries globally.

Box 1: Worked example of a framework for transitioning the fictitious journal *Cutting-Edge Biology* that uses pre-publication filters to the even more fictitious journal *Cutting-Edge Biology 2.0* that uses post-publication filters. The framework is meant to ignite discussion on an extreme end of solutions to the aversive effect of for-profit publishing on science and will likely need refinement in various details depending on the dynamics after initial implementation. Three key requirements need be met for such a transition to work: (i) editor unity – if anything less than a large majority of the editors opted to leave, it would be difficult for a 2.0 journal to become a viable competitor of the initial one; (ii) an understanding from researchers that the editorial team IS the journal; (iii) a convincing argument presented to researchers as to why a manuscript submitted to the 2.0 journal would have the same future audience as the 1.0 option.

Decision and action steps, in chronological order:

- The open-access journal *Cutting-Edge Biology*, published by a for-profit publisher, accepts 20% of the papers submitted based on peer reviewing. Authors pay 5000 EUR article processing charge (APC) per article.
- On Day X, the team of editors' majority of *Cutting-Edge Biology* decide they do not want to continue excluding from publishing in their journal more than half of all scientists globally working in the field due to their incapacity to pay the APCs.
- Negotiations with publisher about reducing the fees to the minimum needed to cover all costs of current quality-assurance and production process end with publisher's decline.
- Team of editors step down and on the same day found a new journal, *Cutting-Edge Biology 2.0*, with a not-for-profit scientific society. The scientific scope remains unchanged. The publication fees are reduced to 100 EUR per paper to cover server and backup costs, also including a budget for complete waivers for authors from outside developed economies. The pre-publication filter is reduced to a screening by editors for any discernible breach of Good Scientific Practice. Papers passing this filter are published the same day online as preprints. Non-anonymous post-publication comments by commenters who identify using their ORCIDs are invited with bots being blocked, and authors can reply to comments and change their paper for six months. Afterwards, the preprints turn into what is called permaprints, continuing to gather comments and replies but without possibility for change by the authors.
- Initial resistance is countered by the team of editors as follows:

fellow editor who voted against journal transformation: "decreased uptake of papers by community!?"; editors: "self-regulation will kick in as soon as community realizes that cutting-edge papers continue being included in the body of papers published; also papers published on pre-print servers over the past two decades were taken up by community"

second critical editor: "why should anyone bother to comment on preprints?"; editors: "yes, incentives will be needed; for example, using the ORCIDs that are mandatory for comments, we will continuously update a

list of who commented on how many preprints, to be mentioned by commenters in their CVs”

author: “reduced visibility and prestige of my paper!?”; editors: “visibility and prestige now given by the number and content of comments made and citations gathered”

reader: “lack of any guidance in searching for relevant papers!?”; editors: “guidance was imperfect also before; comments and citations can be activated to be included in search algorithms”